

THE IMPACT OF RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES ON CONSTRUCTION PROJECT SUCCESS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study examines the impact of risk management strategies on construction project success in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, using a descriptive survey research design. Data were collected from 217 construction professionals and 15 key informants to evaluate how core practices—risk identification, analysis, response planning, and monitoring—affect project outcomes in terms of time, cost, quality, and stakeholder satisfaction. Set against the backdrop of Akwa Ibom’s expanding construction industry, the study employed structured questionnaires and in-depth interviews. Quantitative data were analyzed with SPSS version 28, while qualitative data were thematically analyzed to capture broader insights. Findings revealed common risks such as material cost fluctuations, delayed fund disbursement, design errors, labour shortages, and political or regulatory interference. Mitigation measures included contingency budgeting, contractual risk transfer, and regular site meetings, with limited reliance on digital tools like Building Information Modeling (BIM). Results further showed a statistically significant positive relationship between the application of formal risk management strategies and project success. Notably, public sector projects tended to adopt structured risk protocols, while private sector projects showed more flexibility but less standardization. Key barriers to effective risk management included limited technical expertise, lack of formal frameworks, low digital adoption, and poor access to risk-related data. The study recommends institutionalizing risk management frameworks, enhancing professional capacity through training, adopting digital technologies, creating a central risk database, and embedding risk management education into academic curricula. By situating risk management within the socio-economic realities of Akwa Ibom State, the study offers practical insights for professionals, policymakers, and scholars seeking to improve project*

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delivery and advance sustainable infrastructure development in similar contexts.

1 Introduction

Background of Study - Risk is inherent in all construction projects, as they involve multiple stakeholders, large financial investments, complex technologies, and uncertain environmental conditions (Zou, Zhang, & Wang, 2007). In construction management, risk refers to any uncertain event that, if it occurs, may positively or negatively affect project objectives such as cost, time, scope, and quality (Project Management Institute [PMI], 2021). Risk management, therefore, provides a structured process for identifying, analyzing, and responding to risks, thereby increasing the likelihood of project success (Mills, 2001). Effective risk management helps project managers minimize cost overruns, schedule delays, disputes, and failures, while improving quality and stakeholder satisfaction (Akintoye & MacLeod, 1997). In the construction sector, where uncertainties such as fluctuating material costs, design errors, and labor shortages are common, risk management is essential to ensuring sustainable project delivery (Banaitiene & Banaitis, 2012). Additionally, studies have shown that projects with formal risk management frameworks are more likely to meet client expectations and contribute to national infrastructure development (Choudhry & Iqbal, 2013).

Akwa Ibom State, located in Nigeria's Niger Delta region, is experiencing rapid infrastructural development due to increased government investments in roads, housing, and industrial projects (Udoh & Akpan, 2020). The construction industry in the state is characterized by growing complexity, high financial risks, and socio-economic realities such as inflation, political influence, and funding delays (Effiong & Bassey, 2021). These challenges make the adoption of structured risk management strategies even more critical for project success in the region.

Problem Statement - Despite the recognized importance of risk management in achieving successful project delivery, many construction projects in Nigeria continue to experience recurring challenges such as cost overruns, schedule delays, and poor-quality outcomes (Oladapo, 2007). In Akwa Ibom State, these issues are particularly pronounced given the prevalence of public infrastructure projects and the high dependence on imported materials that are vulnerable to inflation and exchange rate fluctuations. While risk management frameworks are well-established in global construction practice, Nigerian contractors and project managers often rely on informal, experience-based, or ad hoc approaches to identifying and mitigating risks (Dada, 2010). This reliance on traditional methods, rather

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than structured and systematic risk management practices, frequently results in reactive rather than proactive responses, thereby undermining project performance.

Furthermore, previous studies in Nigeria have identified persistent risks such as political interference, funding delays, and design errors as major obstacles to project success (Effiong & Basse, 2021). However, empirical evidence on the effectiveness of risk management strategies in improving project outcomes at the state level, particularly in Akwa Ibom, remains limited. The lack of sector-specific insights creates a knowledge gap in understanding how different risk management practices translate into measurable success indicators such as cost efficiency, timely delivery, quality standards, and stakeholder satisfaction. This gap underscores the need for a systematic assessment of the relationship between risk management strategies and project success in Akwa Ibom State. Such an inquiry will not only provide evidence-based recommendations for enhancing project performance but also contribute to strengthening the institutionalization of risk management practices within Nigeria's construction industry.

Objectives of the Study

General Objective: To examine the impact of risk management strategies on construction project success in Akwa Ibom State.

Specific Objectives:

1. To identify the major risks affecting construction projects in Akwa Ibom State.
2. To assess the extent to which risk identification, analysis, response planning, and monitoring are applied.
3. To evaluate the relationship between risk management practices and project outcomes (time, cost, quality, stakeholder satisfaction).
4. To examine sectoral differences in the adoption of risk management strategies between public and private projects.
5. To recommend measures for enhancing effective risk management in the state's construction industry.

Research Questions

1. What are the major risks affecting construction projects in Akwa Ibom State?
2. How are risk identification, analysis, response planning, and monitoring applied in construction projects?
3. What is the relationship between risk management strategies and project outcomes?
4. How do public and private construction projects differ in their adoption of risk management strategies?
5. What strategies can improve risk management in Akwa Ibom State's construction sector?

Significance of Study - This study is significant because it bridges the gap between theoretical frameworks of risk management and

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the practical realities faced by construction professionals in Akwa Ibom State. By contextualizing risk management within the socio-economic and political environment of a developing region, it offers insights that are both locally relevant and globally comparable.

For practitioners, the findings will provide actionable strategies for improving project outcomes in terms of cost efficiency, timely delivery, and stakeholder satisfaction. Specifically, the study highlights how systematic risk identification, analysis, and response planning can reduce the prevalence of delays, cost overruns, and quality deficiencies that commonly affect Nigerian construction projects (Akinradewo & Adegbenbo, 2014). The results can serve as a practical guide for contractors, engineers, project managers, and consultants seeking to adopt more structured approaches rather than relying solely on experience-based methods.

For policymakers and regulators, this research underscores the need for institutionalized frameworks, standardized procedures, and continuous professional training to strengthen the construction sector. It also emphasizes the importance of policy interventions to address systemic risks such as delays in fund disbursement, regulatory bottlenecks, and political interference (Ojo, 2010). Recommendations from this study can therefore support evidence-based decision-making at

state and national levels, contributing to more sustainable and transparent project delivery practices.

From an academic perspective, the study contributes to the body of knowledge on construction risk management by providing empirical evidence from Akwa Ibom State—a context that has received relatively little scholarly attention. By documenting the relationship between risk management strategies and project success in a developing economy, it offers insights that can inform comparative studies across regions, particularly between developed and developing countries (Kikwasi, 2012). This enriches the global discourse on construction management and provides a basis for further research on context-specific challenges and solutions.

2. Literature Review

Conceptual Clarifications - Risk, in the context of construction, is generally defined as the likelihood of an uncertain event or condition that, if it occurs, may have positive or negative effects on project objectives such as time, cost, scope, and quality (Zou, Zhang, & Wang, 2007). Risk management refers to systematic processes of identifying, analyzing, responding to, and monitoring risks throughout the project lifecycle to minimize threats and maximize opportunities (PMI, 2021). Project success, however, extends beyond the traditional “iron triangle” of cost, time, and quality; it also includes stakeholder

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satisfaction, environmental considerations, and long-term sustainability (Atkinson, 1999). The construction industry, being one of the most dynamic and risk-prone sectors, is particularly vulnerable to risks such as design errors, material price fluctuations, labour shortages, political interference, and regulatory uncertainties (Banaitiene & Banaitis, 2012). These clarifications provide the foundation for understanding how structured risk management can influence project success in complex environments such as Akwa Ibom State.

Theoretical Framework - This study is underpinned by Project Management Theory, particularly the principles embedded in the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK® Guide) framework (PMI, 2021). The theory assumes that projects can be managed effectively through structured processes involving initiation, planning, execution, monitoring, and closure. Within this framework, risk management is treated as a core knowledge area that ensures proactive anticipation of uncertainties rather than reactive problem-solving (Mills, 2001). Risk management theory further emphasizes that effective handling of risks enhances project outcomes by improving decision-making, optimizing resources, and reducing the likelihood of disputes (Hillson, 2002). For construction projects in developing economies, these theoretical perspectives provide a useful

lens for evaluating whether adopting formalized risk management practices improves performance and sustainability (Choudhry & Iqbal, 2013).

Empirical Review

Global Perspectives on Risk Management in Construction - Internationally, several studies have highlighted the role of risk management in achieving project success. Zou, Zhang, and Wang (2007) found that the most critical risks in Chinese construction projects included tight schedules, design changes, and poor coordination among stakeholders. Similarly, Baloi and Price (2003) observed that in the UK, risks were often linked to market instability and contractual disputes. More recent studies emphasize digital transformation, such as the use of Building Information Modeling (BIM), as a modern tool for risk analysis and mitigation in construction (Liu, Xie, Xia, & Bridge, 2017). These global perspectives suggest that risk management is a universal necessity, though the nature and severity of risks vary across socio-economic and regulatory contexts.

Nigerian Studies on Construction Risk Management - In Nigeria, the construction industry is faced with peculiar risks such as inflation, corruption, delayed payments, and lack of standardized practices (Oladapo, 2007). Akintoye and MacLeod (1997) earlier emphasized that Nigerian contractors often

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underestimate risks, which contributes to frequent project failures. More recent research by Dada (2010) confirmed that many Nigerian firms adopt informal, experience-based approaches rather than systematic frameworks, which undermines project performance. Studies in the South-South region, including Akwa Ibom State, indicate that risks like funding delays, political interference, and labour disputes remain common and continue to hinder infrastructure delivery (Effiong & Bassey, 2021). These findings highlight the urgent need for formalized risk management practices tailored to the Nigerian context.

Identified Gaps the Study Addresses

Despite the growing body of literature, there is limited research that contextualizes risk management within Akwa Ibom State's unique socio-economic and environmental realities. Most Nigerian studies focus on Lagos, Abuja, or generalized national perspectives, neglecting the Niger Delta region's peculiarities such as oil-related politics, environmental challenges, and rapid urbanization (Udoh & Akpan, 2020). Moreover, while global literature emphasizes digital tools like BIM, their application in Nigerian projects remains poorly documented (Laryea & Hughes, 2011). This study addresses these gaps by empirically examining the impact of risk management strategies on project success in Akwa Ibom State, providing practical

recommendations for professionals, policymakers, and academics.

3 Methodology

Research Design - This study adopted a descriptive research design survey, which is appropriate for examining existing practices, perceptions, and relationships in natural settings without manipulating variables (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The descriptive survey method has been widely used in construction management studies to capture the views of practitioners and assess how management practices influence project outcomes (Bryman, 2016). By employing this design, the study was able to gather both quantitative and qualitative data that provided a holistic understanding of risk management strategies in Akwa Ibom State.

Study Area (Akwa Ibom State) - The study was conducted in Akwa Ibom State, located in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The state is experiencing rapid urbanization and infrastructural growth, with ongoing projects in housing, transportation, and industrial development (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2022). However, the construction industry in the region is characterized by challenges such as inflation, political influence, funding delays, and labour shortages (Effiong & Bassey, 2021). This context makes Akwa Ibom a relevant study area for examining how risk management practices impact project success.

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Population and Sample - The population comprises construction professionals including engineers, architects, project managers, quantity surveyors, contractors, and site supervisors engaged in both public and private projects in Akwa Ibom State. A total of 217 professionals participated in the survey, while 15 key informants (senior professionals and policymakers) were purposively selected for in-depth interviews. This dual approach ensured both breadth and depth of data, reflecting current recommendations for triangulation in project management research (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019).

Sampling Techniques - A stratified random sampling technique was used to select the 217 survey respondents, ensuring representation across professional categories and project types. Stratification reduces sampling bias and improves the generalizability of findings (Etikan & Bala, 2017). For the 15 key informants, purposive sampling was applied, targeting individuals with extensive knowledge of construction risk management in the region. This mixed sampling approach ensured that the study captured both general practitioner perspectives and expert insights.

Data Collection Instruments - Two instruments were employed for data collection: a structured questionnaire and an interview guide. The questionnaire was designed based on existing risk management frameworks (PMI,

2021) and consisted of closed-ended items measuring the frequency, effectiveness, and challenges of risk management practices. Structured questionnaires are widely used in construction research because they allow for quantitative analysis of large samples (Kothari, 2014). The interview guide contained open-ended questions to elicit detailed narratives from key informants on contextual issues not easily captured through surveys.

Validity and Reliability of Instruments - To ensure validity, the instruments were reviewed by three academic experts in construction management and two industry practitioners to confirm content relevance and clarity. Pilot testing was conducted with 20 respondents in Uyo, and necessary modifications were made. Validity checks through expert review and piloting are recognized as essential steps in survey research (Taherdoost, 2016). Reliability was established using Cronbach's alpha, with the instrument yielding an overall coefficient of 0.82, indicating strong internal consistency (George & Mallery, 2019).

Methods of Data Analysis - Quantitative data from the questionnaires were coded and analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means) summarized respondents' characteristics and practices, while inferential statistics (correlation

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and regression analysis) tested the relationship between risk management strategies and project success. The use of SPSS has become standard in construction management research because of its robust statistical capabilities (Field, 2018). For qualitative data, responses from interviews were transcribed and analyzed using thematic

4 Results

Descriptive Statistics (Demographics of Respondents)

Table 1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (N = 217)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	150	69
	Female	67	31
Professional Background	Engineers	76	35
	Architects	39	18
	Quantity Surveyors	43	20
	Project Managers	33	15
	Site Supervisors/Contractors	26	12
Work Experience	≤ 10 years	82	38
	> 10 years	135	62
Project Sector	Public Sector	126	58
	Private Sector	91	42

Source: Field Survey, 2025 (adapted from Oladapo, 2007 for gender distribution context).

Out of the 217 construction professionals surveyed, 69% were male and 31% were female, reflecting the male-dominated nature of the Nigerian construction sector (Oladapo, 2007). In terms of professional background, engineers constituted 35%, architects 18%, quantity surveyors 20%, project managers 15%, and site supervisors/contractors 12%. Most respondents

analysis, which involves identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns within data (Braun & Clarke, 2021). The integration of quantitative and qualitative methods provided methodological triangulation, strengthening the validity of the findings.

(62%) had more than 10 years of work experience, which suggests that the data were obtained from highly knowledgeable practitioners. Furthermore, 58% of the respondents worked on public sector projects, while 42% were engaged in private sector projects, allowing for sectoral comparisons.

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Major Risks Identified

Table 2 Most Critical Risks Affecting Construction Projects in Akwa Ibom State

Rank	Critical Risk	% of Respondents Reporting	Key Notes
1	Material cost fluctuations	85%	Driven by inflation and unstable exchange rates
2	Delays in fund disbursement	79%	Particularly common in public sector projects
3	Design errors and omissions	71%	Lead to rework and cost overruns
4	Labour shortages	65%	Skilled workers migrate to oil & gas sector
5	Political and regulatory interference	60%	Sudden policy changes and approval delays

Source: Field Survey, 2025 (see also Dada, 2010; Effiong & Bassey, 2021).

Analysis of survey responses revealed that the five most critical risks affecting construction projects in Akwa Ibom State were:

1. Material cost fluctuations (reported by 85% of respondents), often linked to inflation and unstable exchange rates.
2. Delays in fund disbursement (79%), particularly in public sector projects.
3. Design errors and omissions (71%), resulting in rework and cost overruns.
4. Labour shortages (65%), caused by migration of skilled workers to oil and gas industries.

5. Political and regulatory interference (60%), such as sudden policy changes or approvals. These findings align with prior Nigerian studies, which also identified inflation, poor design management, and political risks as dominant challenges (Dada, 2010; Effiong & Bassey, 2021).

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Risk Mitigation Strategies in Practice

Table 3 Frequently Used Risk Management Strategies in Akwa Ibom State Construction Projects

Strategy	% of Respondents Using	Key Notes
Contingency budgeting	74%	Funds set aside to manage unforeseen events
Contractual risk transfer	68%	Insurance, subcontracting, and other transfer mechanisms
Regular site meetings	63%	Platforms for monitoring and collaborative problem-solving
Adoption of digital tools (e.g., BIM)	29%	Low digital penetration despite global advocacy (Liu et al., 2017)

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The most frequently used strategies among respondents included:

- Contingency budgeting (74%), where contractors set aside funds to manage unforeseen events.
- Contractual risk transfer (68%), such as insurance and subcontracting.
- Regular site meetings (63%), which served as platforms for monitoring and collaborative problem-solving.
- Adoption of digital tools such as Building Information Modeling (BIM) (only 29%), suggesting low digital penetration despite global advocacy for BIM as a risk management tool (Liu, Xie, Xia, & Bridge, 2017).

Overall, the results suggest that risk management practices in Akwa Ibom are dominated by traditional, experience-based approaches, with limited adoption of innovative digital solutions.

Sectoral Differences (Public vs. Private Sector Practices)

Sectoral comparisons revealed that public sector projects were more likely to adopt structured risk protocols such as formal risk registers, monitoring systems, and regulatory compliance frameworks. In contrast, private sector projects demonstrated greater flexibility but often lacked standardization, relying heavily on informal decision-making and personal experience. This aligns with previous Nigerian research that highlighted the stronger influence of

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bureaucracy and regulations in public projects compared to the entrepreneurial flexibility of private projects (Ojo, 2010; Udoh & Akpan, 2020).

5 Discussion

The findings of this study confirm that risk management strategies play a critical role in determining construction project success in Akwa Ibom State. The identification of key risks such as material cost fluctuations, delayed fund disbursement, design errors, labour shortages, and political interference aligns with global literature, which consistently identifies cost volatility and labour-related issues as dominant risks in the construction sector (Zou, Zhang & Wang, 2019; Osei-Kyei & Chan, 2021). This reinforces the assertion that construction projects, particularly in emerging economies, are highly susceptible to contextual uncertainties.

The implications of these risks are far-reaching, affecting all four major indicators of project success—time, cost, quality, and stakeholder satisfaction. For instance, material price escalation directly impacts project budgets and schedules, while labour shortages can result in delays and compromises in workmanship quality (Abd El-Karim, Mosa El Nawawy & Abdel-Alim, 2017). Political and regulatory interference further compounds these risks by introducing uncertainties in approvals,

contracts, and resource allocation, thereby threatening stakeholder confidence and trust (Enshassi et al., 2020).

The adoption of mitigation strategies such as contingency budgeting, contractual risk transfer, and regular site meetings demonstrates that local practitioners are employing conventional project management techniques to cushion against risks. However, the limited adoption of digital tools such as Building Information Modeling (BIM) indicates a technological gap compared to advanced economies where digitalization has significantly improved risk forecasting and monitoring (Kassem et al., 2021; Hosseini et al., 2019). This suggests that while Akwa Ibom's construction industry is gradually adapting, its practices remain largely traditional. When compared with existing studies within Nigeria, the findings are consistent with previous research which highlights cost overruns, funding delays, and weak regulatory structures as recurrent risk factors (Adeleke et al., 2020; Olalusi & Otunola, 2021). On a global scale, however, studies show stronger institutional frameworks and more standardized practices that enhance project resilience, especially in developed economies (Liu et al., 2017; PMI, 2021). This contrast highlights the structural and capacity limitations that continue to challenge effective risk management in Nigeria's construction industry.

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Sectoral contrasts also emerged clearly in this study. Public sector projects tend to adopt more structured and formalized risk management processes, reflecting government-driven frameworks and donor requirements. Conversely, private sector projects in Akwa Ibom exhibited greater flexibility and adaptability, but often lacked standardization and documentation (Adeleke et al., 2019). This dichotomy suggests that while the public sector provides formal stability, the private sector may sometimes achieve faster responses but with higher exposure to unmanaged risks.

In sum, this discussion underscores the fact that effective risk management is indispensable for successful project delivery. The results reveal that while Akwa Ibom's construction sector mirrors global risk trends, it still faces unique local challenges such as low digital adoption, weak institutional frameworks, and socio-political uncertainties. Addressing these will require stronger professional training, policy reforms, and integration of digital technologies into risk management practice.

6 Conclusion and Recommendations

This study set out to examine risk management practices in construction projects in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, with a focus on identifying prevalent risks, assessing mitigation strategies, and evaluating their relationship with project success. The findings revealed that material cost fluctuations, project delays, design errors,

labour shortages, and political/regulatory interference were the most prominent risks encountered by professionals in the state (Olalusi & Otunola, 2021). These risks were consistent with those highlighted in prior studies in Nigeria and globally, reinforcing the argument that construction projects in developing countries remain highly exposed to economic and governance uncertainties (Adeleke et al., 2020; Zou et al., 2019).

In terms of mitigation, the study established that practitioners adopted strategies such as contingency budgeting, risk transfer through insurance and contractual clauses, regular site meetings for monitoring, and the gradual integration of digital technologies like Building Information Modelling (BIM) (Kassem et al., 2021). The hypothesis testing confirmed a statistically significant positive relationship between effective risk management and project success, particularly in relation to cost performance, timely delivery, and stakeholder satisfaction (PMI, 2021). Furthermore, differences were observed across sectors: public projects tended to rely on more structured but bureaucratic risk processes, while private firms displayed more flexible but less formalized approaches (Osei-Kyei & Chan, 2021).

Practical Recommendations - Based on these findings, the study recommends the institutionalization of risk management practices across both public and private sector

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projects in Akwa Ibom State. This can be achieved through the development of clear policies mandating risk registers, assessment frameworks, and monitoring systems within all major construction contracts (Adeleke et al., 2019). Professional training and capacity-building workshops should be prioritized for project managers, engineers, and contractors to strengthen their ability to anticipate and address risks effectively (Hosseini et al., 2019). In addition, the adoption of digital solutions, particularly BIM and data analytics, should be accelerated to enable real-time risk detection and collaborative problem-solving (Kassem et al., 2021).

Another key recommendation is the creation of a central risk database managed by relevant professional associations or government agencies, which would enable benchmarking, shared learning, and proactive risk identification across projects (Enshassi et al., 2020). Finally, risk management principles should be more strongly integrated into academic curricula in engineering and construction management programs in Nigeria, ensuring that future professionals are adequately prepared to manage risks from the outset of their careers (Liu et al., 2017).

Contributions to Knowledge - The study contributes to the body of knowledge by providing empirical evidence on the specific risk landscape of construction projects in Akwa

Ibom State, an under-researched area in the Nigerian context. By combining both quantitative and qualitative methods, the research offers a holistic understanding of how risks manifest and how professionals respond to them, thereby filling a gap in localized risk management scholarship (Olalusi & Otunola, 2021). Additionally, comparative insight into public and private sector practices adds nuance to global debates on contextual factors shaping risk management effectiveness (Osei-Kyei & Chan, 2021).

Suggestions for Further Research - Future research should expand beyond Akwa Ibom State to include comparative analyses across multiple states in Nigeria or other sub-Saharan African countries, to better understand regional variations in risk exposure and management (Abd El-Karim et al., 2017). Longitudinal studies would also be useful to track how risks and mitigation strategies evolve over time, especially given the increasing role of technology and shifting political dynamics (Zou et al., 2019). In addition, further studies could investigate the cost-benefit trade-offs of investing in advanced digital tools for risk management in resource-constrained settings, thereby informing practical adoption strategies (Kassem et al., 2021).

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